

The Golden Sample for the cosmological redshift drift test

Catarina M. J. Marques

[10.1093/mnras/stad1007](https://arxiv.org/abs/10.1093/mnras/stad1007)

Based on

Spectroscopy of QUBRICS quasar candidates: 1672 new redshifts and a golden sample for the Sandage test of the redshift drift

Stefano Cristiani ,¹
Konstantina Boutsia ,^{1,2,8}
Fabio Fontanot ¹
and Andrea Trost^{1,4}

¹INAF–Osservatorio Astronomico di Trieste, Via G.B. Tiepolo, 11, I-34143 Trieste, Italy

²IFPU–Institute for Fundamental Physics of the Universe, via Beirut 2, I-34151 Trieste, Italy

³INFN–National Institute for Nuclear Physics, via Valerio 2, I-34127 Trieste, Italy

⁴Dipartimento di Fisica, Sezione di Astronomia, Università di Trieste, via G.B. Tiepolo 11, I-34131 Trieste, Italy

⁵ESO–European Southern Observatory, Karl-Schwarzschild-Strasse 2, D-85748 Garching bei München, Germany

⁶Las Campanas Observatory, Carnegie Observatories, Colina El Pino, Casilla 601, La Serena, Chile

⁷INAF–Osservatorio Astronomico di Padova, Vicolo dell’Osservatorio 5, I-35122 Padova, Italy

⁸Scuola Normale Superiore, P.zza dei Cavalieri, I-56126 Pisa, Italy

⁹Centro de Astrofísica da Universidade do Porto, Rua das Estrelas, P-4150-762 Porto, Portugal

¹⁰Instituto de Astrofísica e Ciências do Espaço, CAUP, Rua das Estrelas, P-4150-762 Porto, Portugal

¹¹Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade do Porto, Rua do Campo Alegre, P-4150-007 Porto, Portugal

Cosmological redshift drift test

What is the optimal sample size?

Golden Sample → QSOs

Why QSOs?

QSO

Cosmic lighthouses/
Brightest non-transient
sources

Unique
view of the
Universe

Precious tools for
studying intergalactic
environments

high z

Through the absorption
spectrum

Where do absorption signatures in the bright high-z QSO spectra lead us?

- Measurement of primordial Deuterium abundance
- Temperature evolution of the CMB
- Variation of the fundamental constants of nature
- Sandage test - detailed study of the QSO's Ly α forest

QUBRICS Survey

QUasars as BRight beacons for Cosmology in Southern hemisphere

(Calderone et al. 2019)

$$z \geq 2.5$$
$$i < 18$$

Compensate the lack of bright QSOs in the southern hemisphere

Several hundred new spectroscopically confirmed bright QSOs

QUBRICS Survey

QUasars as BRight beacons for Cosmology in Southern hemisphere

(Calderone et al. 2019)

Available optical and
IR wide-field surveys
in the South

ML techniques

Thousands of bright
QSO candidates

Confirmation of a few
hundred candidates

Follow-up
Spectroscopy

Secure object type classification

QUBRICS Survey

QUasars as BRight beacons for Cosmology in Southern hemisphere

(Calderone et al. 2019; Guarneri et al. 2021; Guarneri et al. 2022; Calderone et al, in prep)
(Boutsia et al. 2020; Cristiani et al.2023)

Continuous update

Refine selection methods and the applicability range

Continuation of spectroscopic confirmation campaigns

Improve the success rate and completeness

QUBRICS Survey

QUasars as BRight beacons for Cosmology in Southern hemisphere

(Calderone et al. 2019)

One of the main goals

Sample of bright targets for the Sandage test of the cosmological redshift drift

Direct, real-time, and model-independent mapping of the expansion rate of the Universe

» Directly test the Λ CDM paradigm

Cosmological redshift drift test

Sandage test (Sandage 1962)

Cosmic expansion in the cosmological redshifts of many absorption lines in the spectra of bright QSOs

Drift detection

Direct measurement of cosmological parameters

e.g. $\Omega_m, \Omega_\Lambda, H_0$

Synergies with other cosmological probes

Characterization of the physical properties of dark energy

(Martins et al. 2016; Alves et al. 2019; Esteves et al. 2021; Marques et al. 2023)

Cosmological redshift drift test

Sandage test (Sandage 1962)

Tiny effect
 $\sim \text{cm s}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$

High SNR required

Bright QSOs + Large telescopes

Golden Sample

ELT's flagship goal
(Liske et al. 2008)

Golden Sample

(Boutsia et al. 2020; Cristiani et al. 2023)

	Nr targets	Temporal separation	Allocation time	Variable amount of time required to reach $\sigma_v = 22.8 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$
Boutsia et al. 2020	30 QSOs $2.8 < z < 4.8$	25 yr	< 2500 h	
Cristiani et al. 2023	7 QSOs $2.9 < z < 4.8$	25 yr	$1500/7 = 214 \text{ h}$	Fixed for each QSO

Fisher's Matrix Analysis Forecasts

FRIDDA code (Marques et al. 2023)

Cosmological impact of redshift drift measurements

$$\Omega_m = 0.31$$

$$H_0 = h \ 100 = 67.7 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$$

Flat Λ CDM + Planck Collaboration VI (2020) best-fitting cosmological parameters

External priors: $\sigma_h = 0.05$; $\sigma_{\Omega_m} = 0.05$

Uncertainty in the radial velocity measurement (updated from Liske et al. 2008): σ_v

Form factor: $\mathbf{g} = 1$ all the targets are observed twice
 $\mathbf{g} = 1.7$ for a uniform distribution

Fisher's Matrix Analysis Forecasts

FRIDDA code (Marques et al. 2023)

— “Old” Golden Sample $g=1$

— Golden Sample $g=1 \rightarrow \sigma(\Omega_m)=0.03$

- - Golden Sample $g=1.7 \rightarrow \sigma(\Omega_m)=0.04$

— Priors only

- 1000 h reduction in observation time:
- only a **small gain** in the **matter density** constraint is visible;
 - **h** constraint recovers the **prior**.

An ESPRESSO Redshift Drift Experiment

PI: Carlos Martins

Golden
Sample

Conceivable to
start observations

Pilot program

Brightness of the QSOs

Before the ELT

2 QSOs

4 Periods

- P110
- P111
- P112
- P113

An ESPRESSO Redshift Drift Experiment

PI: Carlos Martins

Current upper limits are 3 orders of magnitude larger than the expected signal
(Darling 2012; Cooke 2020)

- **Obtain the first statistics-limited constraint**
- **Improve current bounds by an order of magnitude**
- **Provide a full end-to-end proof of concept for the ANDES experiment at the ELT**

An ESPRESSO Redshift Drift Experiment

PI: Carlos Martins

P111 completed – Aug 2023

ThAr reduction

The Golden Sample for the cosmological redshift drift test

Catarina M. J. Marques

 Catarina.Marques@Astro.up.pt

 github.com/CatarinaMMarques/FisherCosmology